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Appendix S1. List of lab identity numbers, taxon names, taxon distribution, DNA voucher information (including area and year of collection) for newly produced data, and accession numbers for sequences used in the analyses. References are given for sequences taken from GenBank. Ribosomal DNA cistron sequences were extracted from transcriptome sequences published by the 1000 plant (1KP) initiative¹. Taxon distributions were extracted from GBIF². Area names follow the World Geographical Scheme for Recording Plant Distributions³ except the Mediterranean distribution, which refers to an occurrence in either one of the 22 sovereign countries in Europe, Africa and Temperate Asia that borders the Mediterranean Sea.

Lab. ident.	Taxon	Distribution	DNA Voucher	Area/Year of collection	plastid accession number	rDNA cistron accession number
EL002	<i>Isoetes aequinoctialis</i> Welw. ex A.Braun	Southern and Trop. Africa	Kornas 3453 (BR)	Zambia 1973	ON017796	ON010717
EL026	<i>Isoetes azorica</i> Durieu ex Milde	The Azores	Gonalves 2611 (BM)	Azores 1971	ON060511	ON010729
EL017	<i>Isoetes australis</i> S.Williams	Western Australia	Orchard 1274 (MEL)	Australia 1968	ON060521	ON010724
EL030	<i>Isoetes biafrana</i> Alston	Trop. Africa	Le Testu 3016 (BM)	C. Afr. Rep. 1951	ON060504	ON010733
EL012	<i>Isoetes cubana</i> Engelm.	Caribbean; Central America; Mexico	Hickey & Hickey 979 (W)	Mexico 1986	ON060519	ON010721
EL022	<i>Isoetes drummondii</i> A.Braun	Australia	Beaglehole 75018 (MEL)	Australia 1983	ON060513	ON010727
EL027	<i>Isoetes durieui</i> Bory	Mediterranean; SW Europe	Byfield s.n. (BM)	Turkey 1992	ON060505	ON010730
EL028	<i>Isoetes durieui</i> Bory	Mediterranean; SW Europe	De Retz 65141 (BM)	France 1972	ON060506	ON010731
EL013	<i>Isoetes echinospora</i> Durieu	Europe; N. America; Asia-Temperate	Ford 609 (W)	Canada 2006	ON060510	ON010722
	<i>Isoetes flaccida</i> Shuttlew. ex A.Braun	Southeastern USA	---	---	NC_014675 ⁴	---
EL005	<i>Isoetes giessii</i> Launert	Namibia	Giess, Volk & Bleissner 5564 (BR)	Namibia 1963	ON060502	ON010718
EL025	<i>Isoetes lechleri</i> Mett.	Western S. America	Fernandez-Casas & Molero 6619 (BM)	Bolivia 1982	ON060507	ON010728
EL032	<i>Isoetes malinverniana</i> Ces & De Not.	Italy	Raynal 20885 (BR)	Italy 1978	ON060522	ON010734
EL020	<i>Isoetes neoguineensis</i> Baker	Papua New Guinea	Craven 2717 (MEL)	Papua New Guinea 1974	ON060515	ON010725
EL008	<i>Isoetes nigriflora</i> A.Braun	W. Trop. Africa; West-Central Trop. Africa	De Wilde & De Wilde-Duyfjes 3518 (BR)	Cameroon 1964	ON060516	ON010719
EL033	<i>Isoetes occidentalis</i> L.F.Hend.	Subarctic America; Western Canada; Northwestern USA; Southwestern USA	Oettinger & Thorne 1268 (BM)	USA 1969	ON060509	ON010735
EL015	<i>Isoetes pallida</i> Hickey	Mexico	Hickey & Hickey 962 (W)	Mexico 1986	ON060520	ON010723
EL036	<i>Isoetes philippinensis</i> Merr. & L.M.Perry	Malesia	Price 500 (BM)	Philippines 1969	ON060524--ON060589	ON010737
EL021	<i>Isoetes pusilla</i> C.R.Marsden & Chinnock	New South Wales; Victoria	Willis s.n. (MEL)	Australia 1981	ON060512	ON010726
EL039	<i>Isoetes sampathkumaranii</i> L.N.Rao	Indian Subcontinent	Goswami s.n. (BM)	India (unknown year)	ON060514	ON010739
EL035	<i>Isoetes schweinfurthii</i> A.Braun	Trop. Africa	Kers 3130 (BM)	Namibia 1968	ON060518	ON010736
EL037	<i>Isoetes transvaalensis</i> C.Jermy & Schelpe	Southern Africa	Hilliard & Burt 5989 (BM)	South Africa 1969	ON060503	ON010738
EL010	<i>Isoetes weberi</i> Herter	Brazil	Callé 95840 (BR)	Brazil 1935	ON060508	ON010720
EL029	<i>Isoetes welwitschii</i> A.Braun	Trop. Africa	Wingfield 2032 (BM)	Tanzania 1972	ON060517	ON010732
EL057	<i>Isoetes wormaldii</i> Sim.	South Africa	Pocock 20009 (BM)	South Africa 1955	ON060523	ON010740
	<i>Huperzia lucidula</i> (Michx.) Trevis	---	---	---	NC_006861 ⁵	
	~	---	---	---	---	GKAG ¹
	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> L.	---	---	---	MH549642 ⁶	---

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Lab. ident.	Taxon	Distribution	DNA Voucher	Area/Year of collection	plastid accession number	rDNA cistron accession number
	<i>Lycopodium annotinum</i> L.	---	---	---	---	ENQF ¹
	<i>Selaginella kraussiana</i> (Kunze) A.Braun	---	---	---	NC_040926 ⁶	---
	<i>Selaginella moellendorffii</i> Hieron.	---	---	---	HM173080 ⁷	
	~	---	---	---	---	ZZOL ¹
	<i>Selaginella selaginoides</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Schrank & Mart.	---	---	---	---	KUXM ¹
	<i>Aneura mirabilis</i> (Malmb.) Wickett & Goffinet	---	---	---	NC_010359 ⁸	
	<i>Pellia neesiana</i> (Gottsche) Limpr.	---	---	---	---	JHFI ¹
	<i>Marchantia paleacea</i> Bertol.	---	---	---	NC_001319 ⁹	
	~	---	---	---	---	HMHL ¹
	<i>Physcomitrella patens</i> (Hedw.) Bruch & Schimp.	---	---	---	AP005672 ¹⁰	
	<i>Physcomitrium</i> sp.	---	---	---	---	YEPO ¹
	<i>Syntrichia ruralis</i> (Hedw.) F.Weber & D.Mohr	---	---	---	FJ546412 ¹¹	
	<i>Syntrichia princeps</i> (De Not.) Mitt.	---	---	---	---	GRKU ¹
	<i>Anthoceros angustus</i> Steph.	---	---	---	NC_004543 ¹²	
	<i>Anthoceros agrestis</i> Paton	---	---	---	---	BSNI ¹
	<i>Diplopterygium glaucum</i> (Thunb. ex Houtt.) Nakai	---	---	---	NC_024158 ¹³	
	<i>Hymenophyllum cupressiforme</i> Labill.	---	---	---	---	TRPJ ¹
	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> (L.) Kuhn	---	---	---	NC_014348 ¹⁴	
	<i>Lygodium japonicum</i> (Thunb.) Sw.	---	---	---	KF225593 ¹³	
	~	---	---	---	---	PBUU ¹
	<i>Osmundastrum cinnamomeum</i> (L.) C.Presl	---	---	---	NC_024157 ¹³	
	~	---	---	---	---	RFMZ ¹
	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> L.	---	---	---	NC_016986 ¹⁵	
	~	---	---	---	---	SGTW ¹
	<i>Welwitschia mirabilis</i> Hook.f.	---	---	---	NC_010654 ¹⁶	
	<i>Gnetum montanum</i> Markgr.	---	---	---	---	GTHK ¹
	<i>Pinus thunbergii</i> Parl.	---	---	---	D17510 ¹⁷	
	<i>Pinus radiata</i> D.Don	---	---	---	---	DZQM ¹
	<i>Amborella trichopoda</i> Baill.	---	---	---	NC_005086 ¹⁸	
	~	---	---	---	---	URDJ ¹
	<i>Nymphaea alba</i> L.	---	---	---	AJ627251 ¹⁹	
	<i>Nymphaea</i> sp.	---	---	---	---	PZRT ¹
	<i>Nuphar advena</i> (Aiton) W.T.Aiton	---	---	---	DQ354691 ²⁰	
	~	---	---	---	---	WTKZ ¹

Lab. ident.	Taxon	Distribution	DNA Voucher	Area/Year of collection	plastid accession number	rDNA cistron accession number
	<i>Ananas comosus</i> (L.) Merr.	---	---	---	NC_026220 ²¹	
	<i>Typha latifolia</i> L.	---	---	---	---	BRUD ¹
	<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	---	---	---	EF614270 ²²	
	~	---	---	---	---	NPND ¹
	<i>Ranunculus macranthus</i> Scheele	---	---	---	NC_008796 ²⁰	
	<i>Hydrastis canadensis</i> L.	---	---	---	---	VGHH ¹
	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.	---	---	---	JN637766 ²³	
	<i>Amelanchier canadensis</i> (L.) Medik.	---	---	---	---	EAVM ¹
	<i>Veronica nakaiana</i> Ohwi	---	---	---	NC_031153 ²⁴	
	<i>Synphoricarpos</i> sp.	---	---	---	---	CAQZ ¹
	<i>Plantago maritima</i> L.	---	---	---	NC_028519 ²⁵	
	~	---	---	---	---	YKZB ¹

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